

Typification and Characteristics of Digital Safe Spaces: A literature review

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Appendix 1

Table 1. Final set of papers

Primary/ Backward/ Forward search	Outlet	Name of paper	Authors	Year
Primary	HICSS	Social Media and the Black Travel Community: From Autonomous Space to Liberated Space	Sutherland T.	2019
Primary	HICSS	Safe Spaces & Free Speech: Effects of Moderation Policy on Structures of Online Forum Discussions	Gibson A.	2017
Primary	ICIS	How Do Online Communities of Patients Aggregate on Twitter? An Affordance Perspective	Bernardi R.	2016
Primary	HICSS	Mining for Social Skills: Minecraft in Home and Therapy for Neurodiverse Youth	Zolyomi, A. and Schmalz, M.	2017
Primary	HICSS	How do the women of Open Source support each other?	Singh, V. and Brandon, W.	2020
Primary	ISJ	Creating convivial affordances: A study of virtual world social movements	McKenna B.	2020
Primary	ITP	The role of blogs in restoring the self-integrity of women victims of intimate partner sexual violence	Watanabe C.Y.V.; Diniz E.H.; Scornavacca E.	2022
Primary	ACM-HCI	Moderation as Empowerment: Creating and Managing Women-Only Digital Safe Spaces	Ammari T., Nofal M., Naseem M., Mustafa M.	2022
Primary	ACM-HCI	“We Gather Together We Collaborate Together”: Exploring the Challenges and Strategies of Chinese Lesbian and Bisexual Women’s Online Communities on Weibo	Cui Y., Yamashita N., Lee Y.-C.	2022
Primary	ACM-HCI	Trans Time: Safety, Privacy, and ContentWarnings on a Transgender-Specific Social Media Site	Haimson O.L., Buss J., Weinger Z., Starks D.L., Gorrell D., Baron B.S.	2020
Primary	ACM-HCI	Safe enough to share: Setting the dementia agenda online	Lazar A., Dixon E.	2019
Primary	ACM-HCI	Social Norm Vulnerability and its Consequences for Privacy and Safety in an Online Community	Dym B., Fiesler C.	2020
Primary	ACM-HCI	More than a Modern Day Green Book: Exploring the Online Community of Black Twitter	Klassen S., Kingsley S., McCall K., Weinberg J., Fiesler C.	2021
Backward	ACM-HCI	Safe Spaces and Safe Places: Unpacking Technology-Mediated Experiences of Safety and Harm with Transgender People	Scheuerman M.K., Branham S., and Hamidi F.	2018
Backward	ACM-CSCW	Making “Safe”: Community-Centered Practices in a Virtual World Dedicated to Children with Autism	Ringland K., Wolf C., Dombrowski L., and Hayes G.	2015
Backward	Computers in Human Behavior	Nurturing health-related online support groups: Exploring the experiences of patient moderators	Coulson, N.S. and Shaw, R.L.	2013
Backward	ACM-HCI	Social support, reciprocity, and anonymity in responses to sexual abuse disclosures on social media	Andalibi N., Haimson O., De Choudhury M., and Forte A.	2018
Forward	Computers in Human Behavior	Resistance and Sexuality in Virtual Worlds: An LGBT Perspective	McKenna B., and Chughtai H.	2020
Forward	ACM-HCI	“It’s a lonely disease”: Cultivating Online Spaces for Social Support among People Living with Dementia and Dementia Caregivers	Johnson J., Arnold V., Piper A.M., Hayes G.	2022
Forward	Sociology of Crime	Hatred She Wrote: A Comparative Topic Analysis of Extreme Right and Islamic State Women-Only Forums	Lokmanoglu A., Veilleux-Lepage Y.	2020

Appendix 2

Figure 1. PRISMA-inspired visualization of the data collection process

Appendix 3

Table 2. Concept matrix

Type of Digital Safe Space	Main Associated Characteristics	
	Space context	Participant perceptions
Supportive	Designed support, digital platforms affordances (anonymity), resource-intensive work	Emergent support, triggers, (perceived) freedom
Confirmative	Boundaries, rules, digital platform affordances (connectivity and communication)	Reaffirmation, homogeneity, emergent support, triggers, (perceived) freedom
Activistic	Digital platform affordances (anonymity), rules, boundaries, designed support	(Perceived) freedom, triggers, emergent support, homogeneity

Appendix 4

Table 3. Examples of identified triggers

Type of group	Identified triggers
Black traveler community (Klassen et al., 2021; Sutherland, 2019)	Racism, appropriation, exclusionary and hostile spaces to Black travelers
LGBT community (Cui et al., 2022; Haimson et al., 2020; McKenna, 2020; McKenna & Chughtai, 2020; Scheuerman et al., 2018)	Discrimination, prejudice, stigma, harassment, violence, homophobia, transphobia
Medical condition / patients (Coulson & Shaw, 2013; Johnson et al., 2022; Lazar & Dixon, 2019; Ringland et al., 2015)	Judgment, criticism, stigma, discrimination, cyberbullying, harassment
Abuse victims (Andalibi et al., 2018; Watanabe et al., 2022)	Rape culture, stigma, adverse social contexts